

Table S1 Collection details for Chinese house rats specimens use in this study. Note that code for location corresponds to Fig. 1 and that clade corresponds to the lineage (*R. norvegicus*: N and *R. tanezumi*: T)

Code	County, province	Coordinates	No.	Clade	mtDNA Haplotype no.	RADSseq
MH	Mohe, Heilongjiang	52°97'N; 122°53'E	27	N	N20-23, N25	2
MS	Jiamusi, Heilongjiang	46°81'N; 130°28'E	10	N	N18, N28, N90-91	
SY	Songyuan, Jilin	45°11'N; 124°49'E	14	N	N50, N53-54, N92-96	1
MJ	Mudanjiang, Heilongjiang	44°58'N; 129°60'E	16	N	N27, N79, N86-87, N89	
SL	Shuangliao, Jilin	43°76'N; 123°70'E	6	N	N50, N56, N78, N80, N82	
UQ	Urumqi, Xinjiang	43°46'N; 87°36'E	15	N	N4	2
BT	Baotou, Inner Mongolia	40°64'N; 109°84'E	21	N	N1, N15-16, N30, N55, N61-63, N65, N67-68, N70, N72, N75-76, N100	1
CY	Chaoyang, Liaoning	39°95'N; 116°49'E	5	N	N51-52, N83	
DL	Dalian, Liaoning	38°94'N; 121°59'E	20	N	N5, N25-26, N58-59, N64, N69, N84-85, N88	2
YP	Yuanping, Shanxi	38°83'N; 112°68'E	39	N	N34-38, N41-44, N47-49	1
QX	Qinxian, Shanxi	36°70'N; 112°65'E	5	N	N19, N33, N42	
LI	Linshu, Shandong	34°89'N; 118°73'E	30	N	N15, N60-61, N65-67, N71-74, N77, N100	2
TS	Tianshui, Gansu	34°58'N; 105°73'E	2	T	T6	
HZ	Hanzhong, Shaanxi	33°08'N; 107°04'E	5	N	N29	
RG	Rugao, Jiangsu	32°27'N; 120°58'E	23	T	T5-6, T8, T13, T18-19, T27	
MY	Mianyang, Sichuan	31°50'N; 104°70'E	6	N, T	N29, N32, N98, N102, T6	6
YM	Yunmeng, Hubei	31°00'N; 113°77'E	32	T	T6, T22-23, T28-29, T31-33	
CD	Chengdu, Sichuan	30°67'N; 104°06'E	34	N, T	N1-2, N17, N24, N29, N99, T2, T6-7, T9, T11-12, T21, T24	30
HS	Huangshi, Hubei	30°21'N; 115°05'E	5	N, T	N57, T6	3
LS	Lhasa, Tibet	29°66'N; 91°11'E	23	T	T4, T6	2
JW	Jianwei, Sichuan	29°23'N; 103°98'E	7	N, T	N1, N3, N10, T6, T25	5
JJ	Jiangjin, Chongqing	29°03'N; 106°26'E	8	N	N81, N97-98, N101	2
LZ	Luzhou, Sichuan	28°89'N; 105°44'E	10	N	N46, N98	
CS	Changsha, Hunan	28°21'N; 112°97'E	33	N, T	N103, T6, T9-10, T20, T30	31
LD	Loudi, Hunan	27°74'N; 111°99'E	5	T	T29, T35	
JO	Jian'ou, Fujian	27°04'N; 118°48'E	9	N, T	N13-14, N75, T6, T26	8
KL	Kaili, Guizhou	26°63'N; 107°94'E	4	T	T29, T3, T34	
KM	Kunming, Yunnan	25°04'N; 102°72'E	22	N, T	N6-7, N29, N31, T6	2
ZP	Zhaoping, Guangxi	24°01'N; 110°97'E	3	T	T9	
GD	Guangzhou, Guangdong	23°13'N; 113°25'E	27	N, T	N39-40, N45, T1, T6, T14-T17, T36	22
ZJ	Zhanjiang, Guangdong	21°25'N; 110°36'E	20	N	N8-9, N11-12, N45	2